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Microbial Contamination of Eggs and Defence Systems

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the routes of microbial contamination in eggs and the protective mechanisms. Contamination of eggs with bacteria before ovulation is unusual and contamination most commonly occurs after ovulation. The egg has various mechanisms, both physical and chemical, to protect its contents from bacterial contamination. The first barrier is the uneven organic layer over the shell, the cuticle. The next barrier is the shell, and the thickness of the shell plays an important role in preventing bacterial penetration. Eggshell membranes do not have an inherent antibacterial property and can be penetrated by bacteria. Albumin is both a chemical and physical barrier, and pH, conalbumin and lysozyme enzyme play an important role in this defense. Albumin is both a chemical and physical barrier. Conalbumin, pH and lysozyme enzyme play an important role in this defence system.

Key Words: Eggs, bacteria, contamination, defence system.

INTRODUCTION

Eggs produced for both table and incubation are constantly under threat from pathogens. It appears that the egg has several mechanisms, both physical and chemical, to protect its contents from bacterial contamination. While at the time of laying, the number of bacteria on the shell of an egg may range from 300 to 500, in an adequate environment, this number may increase rapidly so that one hour after the egg is laid there could be 20,000 to 30,000 bacteria present (North and Bell, 1990). Typical contaminants are *Micrococcus*, *Salmonella*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Escherichia* (Mayes and Takeballi, 1983), but molds have also been identified (Bruce and Johnston, 1978). In this review, pre- and post-ovulation contamination of eggs and their defense systems are discussed.

Pre-ovipositional contamination

The contamination of eggs with bacteria prior to oviposition is not usual. However, Harry (1963a) was able to recover *Lactobacillus* spp. and *Micrococcus* spp. from the ova. The exact mechanism of the infection is not yet clear, but it is known that for instance *Salmonella* spp. (*S. enteritidis* and host-specific *S. gallinarum*, *S. pullorum*) are able to pass to the ova from the alimentary canal, via the blood (Gordon and Tucker, 1965). Harry (1963a) suggested the possibility of direct infection of the ovarian tissue itself; however, infection of the ova can occur in the oviduct as well. Thus, while *Micrococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *coli-aerogenes* organisms are the dominant contaminants isolated from the oviduct (Harry 1963a), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Pasteurella* spp. have also been recovered (Mayes and Takeballi, 1983). Harry (1963a) contended that contamination of the oviduct occurs from the cloacal region and was often due to careless artificial insemination.

The microbial flora found in the oviduct (Harry, 1963a; Jacobs *et al.*, 1978; Bruce and Drysdale, 1991) is, however, markedly different from that of the contaminated egg, indicating the low risk of transovarian

infection. Thus, when Bruce and Drysdale (1991), examined the oviduct of end-of-lay broiler breeder hens they observed that the rate of contamination was 63%, compared with 4% for the unhatched eggs. This shows that bacterial infection of the reproductive tract does not necessarily result in the production of contaminated eggs. It has been demonstrated (Brooks and Taylor, 1955; Board, 1977) and is widely accepted that at least 90% of eggs are free of internal bacterial contaminants at oviposition.

Post-ovipositional contamination

Contamination occurs most frequently after oviposition, the organisms entering the egg by penetrating the shell, through the pores. Contaminants may be divided into pathogens (e.g. *Salmonella enteritidis*) or spoilage bacteria (e.g. *Aeromonas*, *Enterobacter*, *Proteus*, *Pseudomonas*). Organisms such as these contaminate the shell surface as the egg passes through the cloaca and comes into contact with the cage floor or nest box.

Microbial contaminants enter the egg via, in the case of the domestic fowl, the some 10,000 pores that traverse the shell. Pores have a broad entrance on the surface (~ 20 µm) leading to a channel (mean diameter 11.9 µm) which penetrates the crystal layers and terminates between the mammillary knobs (Parsons, 1982). Due to the relative size of the pore canal and bacteria, the pores do not present a barrier to these contaminants. Indeed, a positive correlation has been found between porosity and bacterial penetration (Fromm and Munroe, 1960). Haines and Moran (1940) have demonstrated that yeasts, which are considerably larger than bacteria, are able to pass through the pores. If eggs are stored in humid conditions, the growth of molds on the shell surface may be promoted. It has been stated (Mayes and Takeballi, 1983) that the growth of mold hyphae facilitates the enlargement of pores, which in turn, helps the entry of bacteria into the egg.

The internal body temperature of adult laying birds is between 40.6°C and 41.7°C (Sturkie, 1986), therefore, once the egg is laid, it starts to lose heat, and as the contents cool, they shrink so producing internal suction that also helps bacteria to penetrate the shell.

A further, very important agent for bacterial penetration is the presence of water on the surface of the shell or in the pore canal. When the egg and water are at the same temperature, water is drawn in by capillary attraction whereas it is actively drawn in when the egg is warmer than its surroundings (Haines and Moran, 1940). As the water is taken up by the egg so microorganisms on the shell are carried through the pores (Orel, 1959).

Microbial defense systems of the egg

The infection of an egg can be divided into three stages: 1) contamination and penetration of the shell; 2) colonization and penetration of the shell membranes; 3) infection of the contents (Board, 1964). The egg has evolved a range of physical and chemical defences to prevent the majority of bacteria in the environment from gaining access to the developing embryo.

The first barrier is the uneven organic layer over the shell, the cuticle. The cuticle is moist (immature) on the newly laid egg and requires some 60 seconds after egg laying to irreversibly change into a more solid, mature form. Contact with bacteria during this immature period results in a substantial number of bacteria penetrating the shell (Sparks and Board, 1985). However, once it has gained its mature state, the cuticle plugs the pores and resists the movement of solids (such as feces, mud) and liquids (water) into the pore channel (Sparks, 1985). In this way, although pores represent potential entrances for bacteria, only the few (around 100) so called “patent pores”, which are not properly covered by the cuticle, are readily penetrated if challenged.

The next barrier is the shell. Sauter and Peterson (1974) contended that shell thickness played an important role in preventing bacterial penetration. Their findings (Table 1) show that shell quality is more important than time in resisting bacterial penetration. While only 11% of the bacteria penetrated the shells of good quality (thick) shells after 30 minutes, this figure had increased to 34% for poor quality shells.

Table 1. Relationship between shell quality and bacterial penetration.

Shell quality	% Bacterial penetration of shell		
	After 30 min.	After 60 min.	After 24 hr.
Poor	34	41	54
Average	18	25	27
Good	11	16	21

Source: Sauter and Peterson, (1974).

Other workers (Williams *et al.*, 1968; Vadhera *et al.*, 1970 and Drysdale, 1985), however, found no correlation between shell thickness and the percentage bacterial penetration.

Three phases of bacterial growth (Board, 1966) have been observed after the penetration of the shell of the newly laid egg: i) a 2-4 days phase of primary multiplication, ii) a lag of 10 to 20 days, iii) a secondary phase of multiplication. The lag phase before the recovery of large numbers of organisms from the albumen had been first associated with the shell membranes. It has been postulated that, by acting as a bacterial filter, the shell membranes are important barriers to bacterial transmission (Haines and Moran, 1940; Garibaldi and Stokes, 1958; Kraft *et al.*, 1958). However, Garibaldi and Stokes (1958) noted that this property is only temporary. Board (1964) investigated the role of shell membranes in bacterial penetration and reported that inoculating the air cell of a newly laid egg with a small inoculum resulted in a relatively small increase in the size of the population in the inner membrane. When a large inoculum was used, the albumen was invaded but multiplication did not occur. The author took this to be an indication that the "filtering property" of the membrane was minimal. When bacteria multiply in the membrane, the rate and extent of multiplication is controlled in part by the nature and availability of the nutrients present. This, primary, phase of multiplication ends 2-4 days following inoculation. The death of organisms in the membranes or their migration to the albumen results in a gradual decline, in the 10-20 days lag period. The secondary phase of multiplication will occur either when the yolk makes contact with the inner shell membrane or when bacteria migrate through the albumen to the yolk. During this phase the albumen is grossly infected, and the organisms utilize the glucose present in the albumen (Board, 1964; Board and Ayres, 1965; Board, 1966). The restriction of bacterial multiplication by the shell membranes is primarily due to the physical and chemical antimicrobial properties of the albumen (Brooks, 1960; Board, 1964; Board and Ayres, 1965; Board, 1966).

The albumen's physical barrier relies upon two components: i) the viscosity of the proteins and ii) the organisation of the albumen that maintains the greatest possible distance between the yolk and the shell membranes. Board (1977) and Yadav and Vadehra (1977) reported that the viscosity of albumen proteins restricts bacterial movement. The albumen has a swollen rigid gel structure composed mainly of β -ovomucin, a disulfide bonded glycoprotein complex (Robinson and Monsey, 1972). During storage, however, the gel-like structure is gradually lost causing a "thinning" of the albumen. Various mechanisms, such as hydrolysis by protease enzymes, depolymerisation by hydroxyl ion, interaction with disulfide bond reducing agents can depolymerise ovomucin. With thinning, the albumen does not only lose its bacteria-restricting property but also allows the yolk to float up and make contact with the shell membrane.

The albumen also acts as a chemical barrier (Board, 1969; O'Leary and Busta, 1974), in fact, this is its main defence mechanism of which the most important components are conalbumin, lysozyme, and the alkaline pH of about 9.5 (Board 1966, 1969). Some of the antimicrobial compounds of the egg white are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Main antimicrobial substances of the albumen of the hen's egg, and their biological activities.

Component	Action
Lysozyme	Lysis of cell walls of Gram positive bacteria, Flocculation of bacterial cells
Conalbumin	Chelation of Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+}
Avidin	Combination with biotin
Ovomucoid	Inhibition of trypsin

Source: Board, 1966; Board and Tranter, 1986

There is a synergistic effect between the albumen's pH and antimicrobial proteins. The pH of the albumen of the freshly laid egg is 7.6-7.9 but rapidly increases to over 9 (Romanoff and Romanoff, 1949). This increase in pH is caused by the loss of carbon dioxide. The efficacy of antimicrobial proteins such as conalbumin is dependent on hydrogen ion concentration (Garibaldi 1960), but the high pH is also germicidal (Garibaldi 1960; Board and Tranter, 1986). Tranter and Board (1982) highlighted the chelating property of one of the more important antimicrobial proteins, conalbumin (ovotransferrin) (see also Schade and Caroline, 1944; Alderton *et al.*, 1946). It strongly (dissociation constant of about 10^{-29} M) binds iron ions which thus become unavailable to bacteria for multiplication, etc. (Donovan *et al.*, 1976). Several investigators (Garibaldi, 1960; Brooks, 1960; Board, 1964) showed that the inhibition of bacterial growth can be overcome by the addition of iron or by the modification of the pH. Thus washing eggs with water contaminated with iron salts can promote bacterial growth. Conalbumin also binds copper thus maintaining the bactericidal properties of lysozyme, which are inhibited by this metal (Gilbert, 1971).

The enzyme lysozyme is also part of the defence system. This is the only albumen protein known to directly affect bacteria (Palmer and Guillet Jr, 1991). The lysis of bacteria (*B. subtilis*) was first observed by Laschtschenko in 1909, but the nature of the phenomenon was described only in 1922 by Fleming (Board, 1968). Lysozyme acts on the bacterial cell wall. The cytoplasmic membrane (the cell wall) of bacteria is a macromolecular net consisting of mucopeptides which are linked together in part by β -1-4- and β -1-6 glycosidic and in part by peptide bonds. Lysozyme hydrolyses the β -1-4 bonds (Board, 1968; Geoffroy and Bailey, 1975) thereby lethally disrupting the cell wall integrity. Due to the more complex structure of their cell wall, Gram-negative bacteria are less sensitive to lysozyme than Gram-positive organisms. This, at least in part, might explain the lower number of Gram-positive bacteria in rotten eggs (Board, 1966).

CONCLUSION

Eggs contaminated with microorganisms play a significant role in the spread of diseases in poultry production. Furthermore, microorganisms cause reduced hatchability, poor-quality chick production, and increased early chick mortality. Also, foodborne diseases are a significant health problem for humans (Milakovic-Novak, Prukner, 1990). Eggs are quite rich in nutritional content and are also nutritious for all living organisms, including bacteria. In other words, eggs are a food item that is extremely susceptible to contamination. Once the bacteria find a stable environment, they divide rapidly and colonize the contents of the egg. (Abebe, Gugsu and Ahmed 2020). This review has shown that egg contamination is inevitable. Therefore, despite the egg's natural defense mechanisms, microbial contamination remains a constant concern (Mkangara 2023).

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